

Good Governance and Neo-Liberal Public Policy Formation

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ABSTRACT

Since the last few years, good governance discourse has colonized public discourse on reform and democratization in Indonesia. This article aims to deconstruct the good governance discourse itself, what is actually wrong or perhaps even what is often said about good governance. This article attempts to show the inclusion of neo-liberal ideas in the imagination of political, economic and social changes that took place in the final years of Suharto's leadership in the early 1990s. As will be shown in this article, this movement labeled governance is actually increasingly moving away from the true spirit of governance. In short, the good governance movement in Indonesia actually deviated from the spirit of governance which prioritizes accommodation, cooperation and synergy in equality between actors. This brings about a process of marginalization of economic, social, cultural and political policies that are in line with neo-liberal values.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the terminology of good governance has hit all levels of society in all corners of the archipelago. The slogan for political reform, which was once very popular and energetic in 1998-1999, apparently did not last very long, and was no longer widely used. However, the discourse of good governance can still survive today, and seems to be a symbol of Indonesia's entry into global living standards. Villagers who don't speak English can also pronounce good governance fluently.

It is easy for us to see or hear up close the polite and elegant language of 'good governance', but it is also very easy to see around us that there is systematic corruption, legalization of bribery between power institutions, violations of human rights and other imperial policies. It seems that there is a slight difference between what is called 'good' and 'bad' (bad) or 'poor' (poor) in government governance, because the two go hand in hand like a train track that is designed to be strong anchored by 'bearings' theory and mystification of power, which goes in and out of stations carrying (read: trading) as many passengers as possible. Just like 'good governance' which is injected from one country to another which spreads the influence of absolute truth in administration and public management (Wiratraman, 2008).

In the context of Indonesia which is struggling with demands for reform, good governance appears as a new transplantative model which is believed to be able to treat political bureaucracy which is considered to be full of corruption, bribery and abuse of power, including various violations of human rights. The state bureaucratic apparatus, from the President at the top of the state leadership to the lowest level of government, uniformly sings about good governance. At the level of non-state actors, the agenda of non-governmental organizations also talks a lot about good governance, and has made it a significant work program in post-1998. It is not surprising that anti-corruption programs, supervision of the government and regional autonomy, monitoring judiciary, and so on. Likewise, academics, institutions or donor countries, and other actors talk about the same thing about the importance of good governance.

Uniquely, in the more than a decade of reform that has taken place since 1998, corruption has not decreased but has become more prevalent. The public bureaucracy has not changed much, from a mentality of poor service and inefficiency, the practice of bribery is still prolific, and various violations of human rights still occur. In essence, a corrupt country still cannot be overcome with good governance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The following article will deconstruct the good governance discourse itself, what is actually wrong or perhaps even what is often said about good governance. This article attempts to show the inclusion of neo-liberal ideas in the imagination of political, economic and social changes that took place in the final years of Suharto's leadership in the early 1990s. As will be shown in this article, this movement labeled governance is actually increasingly moving away from the true spirit of governance. In short, the good governance movement in

Indonesia has deviated from the spirit of governance which prioritizes accommodation, cooperation and synergy in equality between actors. This brings about a prolonged process of economic, social, cultural and political marginalization. Therefore, at the end of this article we try to put forward ideas for developing a more democratic and just governance pattern.

METHODS

Since the late 1980s, the term governance began to be used in a different sense. When the term governance was popularized, the change in use of the term from government to governance was intended to indicate the need for a new wave of government reform. The terms government reform, democracy and the like are considered to have experienced inflation and are unable to attract attention to mobilize the spirit of reform. Therefore, new packaging is needed for government reform this time, which is different from previous reforms. According to Rhodes (Pratikno, 2005) the use of the term governance is used to emphasize the need for a new direction and spirit of government reform. The term governance has been used to emphasize the significance of the need to change government processes, methods and achievements.

The use of the term governance as a concept that is different from government, began to be popularized effectively by the World Bank since 1989. In its very famous report entitled "Sub-Saharan Africa: From Crisis to Sustainable Growth". In this report, the World Bank (1989) defines governance as "the exercise of political power to manage the nation". Furthermore, the report emphasizes that political legitimacy and consensus are prerequisites for sustainable development. State actors (government), business and civil society must work together to build consensus, and the role of the state is no longer regulative, but only facilitative. Therefore, Abrahamsen (Wiratraman, 2007) stated that political legitimacy and consensus which are the main pillars of the World Bank's version of Good Governance can only be built by involving the widest possible range of non-state actors and limiting the involvement of the state (government).

With reference to the African case, the argument throughout the report emphasizes that governments are the source of development failure. Therefore, to build good governance, the government must be reduced (less government). Big government will be the source of bad governance. This bad governance, in the World Bank's operations (Weiss 2000: 801) is an unrepresentative government and an inefficient non-market system, which in practice is a source of development failure in Africa (Pratikno, 2005).

Since then, the beginning of a wave of injections in an effort to eradicate 'diseases' in the third world was carried out, by requiring a number of requirements from the World Bank (which were then followed by other donor institutions and countries). The crisis in Africa has brought a clear message in introducing a new concept to combat what the World Bank identifies as a 'crisis of governance' or 'bad governance' (World Bank 1992). Of course, in injecting such governance ideas, discourse was also introduced as a "sweetener" so that it could be accepted and legitimized by the dictatorial powers that were in power

at that time. The "sweetening" discourse is the promotion of democracy which strengthens good governance both as a goal and a requirement for development cooperation. The discourse initiated by the World Bank continues to spread, which then makes good governance a popular slogan, including in Indonesia. This main idea of seeing the government as a source of problems rather than a solution continues to spread, and has given rise to a definition of governance that places more emphasis on the role of actors outside the government (Wiratraman, 2007).

RESULTS

The concept of governance according to Stoker (Kurniawan, 2006) is the development of a governing style where the boundaries between the public sector and the private sector become blurred. This blurring of boundaries is in line with the need for modern countries to be more involved in political mechanisms and recognition of the importance of issues involving empathy and the ability of the public to get involved, thereby providing opportunities for social and political mobilization. The government will have an important role in creating a conducive government political environment, the private sector creates jobs and income, while the community plays a positive role in social, economic and political interactions (Rakhmat, 2009). In the World Bank perspective (Wiratraman, 2008), governance is defined as a matter of power aimed at managing the country's social and economic resources for development. The African experience after the debt crisis and after the cold war has become the background and climate that illustrates the insistence of free market forces and liberal democracy. Good governance in this context is the political imposition of law controlled by industrial countries and international agents (institutions and donor countries) in forming market-oriented governance (Stokke 1995; Gathii 1998). This is good governance that was born from the womb of the big globalization agenda constructed by neo-liberal ideology (Wiratraman, 2008).

To show a quite sharp difference with the definition above, the Tokyo Institute of Technology emphasizes that "[t]he concept of governance refers to the set of values, norms, processes and institutions by which society manages its development and resolves conflict, formally and informally ." (www.soc.titech.ac.jp). In this definition, the meaning of governance is actually emphasized on the behavior and capacity of society to manage common interests, including the capacity to utilize the government in solving public problems (Pratikno, 2005).

The large countries that are members of the OECD define governance as "the use of political authority and exercise of control in a society in relation to the management of its resources for social and economic development". More specifically, the British government, in this case ODA, explains the characteristics of good government including legitimacy, accountability, competence, respect for law and human rights. The World Bank puts forward the characteristics of good governance as: a

strong and participatory civil society; open; predictable policy making; responsible executive; professional bureaucracy; and clear legal rules. Meanwhile, The Commission on Global Governance defines governance as "the sum of the many ways individuals and institutions, public and private, manage their common affairs". In the language of this commission, Weiss (Pratikno, 2005) governance is a continuous process through which differences in interests are accommodated and realized in practice.

Both as sound development management and as democratic politics, reforms towards good governance emphasize the need to reduce the role of government. As defined by Rhodes (1996), good governance is interpreted as a minimal state. This reduction in the role of government requires a greater role for actors outside the government, including Civil Society Organizations, and especially market players.

Looking at the governance formulations above, the key word in the governance concept is consensus through which differences in interests can be accommodated, and synergy can be built. Apart from hoping that state institutions will work well, governance also refers to strengthening market and civil society institutions to offset state domination which was previously a source of development failure. The question then is, what is the problem with governance? What is the connection with neo-liberalism and what implications does it have for the practice of public administration and management? Therefore, the debate about the concepts of governance and good governance needs to be discussed at the level of its application in the third world, especially in Indonesia, and then theoretical reflections that can be built from there.

P Criticism of good governance is nothing new, because many studies or research have been carried out to dismantle this discourse in various approaches, be it political, economic, historical, legal, international sociology, international relations and other disciplinary approaches. The World Bank was the originator of the idea which introduced it as a 'public sector management program', in the context of creating good governance within the framework of development assistance requirements (Pratikno, 2005). Good governance in this context is the "voice of development". As a "voice of development", in fact he is more visible about democratic discipline or a certain model of governance. The crisis in Africa has brought such a clear message in triggering a new concept of 'governance' to oppose what the World Bank calls a 'crisis of governance' or 'bad governance' (World Bank 1992). Africa's experience after the debt crisis and cold war has illustrated the backdrop of a general climate in favor of free markets and liberal democracy, and this has powerfully demonstrated how good governance is a legal political imposition by advanced industrialized countries and international agents (including institutions and donor countries). In shaping market governance (Abrahamsen 2000; Stokke 1995; Gathii 1998).

In the Asian context, good governance projects have long been introduced to a number of countries, especially to countries that are dependent on foreign debt assistance. This project does not care at all about the regime in

power being a corrupt and dictatorial regime. In Indonesia, in the early 1990s, a governance model that was friendly to market interests began to be introduced, through a structural adjustment program scenario. However, when Soeharto was still in power, the projects developed in Indonesia practically failed and could not be accounted for. In fact, the corruption carried out on foreign debt assistance was known to the World Bank, but the World Bank ignored the corrupt debts. This is what is called 'criminal debt', which ironically must be paid by the people and is imposed on the nation's post-Soeharto generation (Winters 1999; 2002).

So, what is referred to as 'aid' by the World Bank, is actually a systematic process of destruction which was not only aimed at the people when the Soeharto regime was in power, but also at the cost of 'perpetuating dictatorial power' which had long-term consequences for millions of Indonesian people in the following years. In such a situation, it is clear that 'good governance' is friendly to hidden mechanisms that have no interest in democratization and human rights. The World Bank's pressure in matters of governance reform became increasingly stronger after the financial crisis in Asia in the latter half of the 1990s. Practice and The World Bank's justification through a diagnosis between 'bad and good' governance became the main discourse in influencing the factors of failure in the context of the crisis, and this is exactly what was done previously in Africa in the 1980s. Along with the reform movement carried out by students in 1998, it was as if neo-liberal proponents were given an 'entrance' to re-invest their projects (also through debt) in the government. Hundreds of millions of dollars are disbursed to the government to finance the reform of public policies and political, legal and economic institutions, so that it is inevitable that good governance will become the mainstream of bureaucratic and legal reform as a support for governance projects

The decentralization that occurred at the beginning of reform has smoothed and fertilized the discourse of good governance, because it has become something sexy, fresh, popular, and said repeatedly by both high-ranking officials and the lowest levels in the regions. Without exception, movement agendas have also become moderated and believe in good governance as a panacea for Indonesia's political-economic bureaucratic order. Academics and non-governmental organizations are also eager to pronounce this discourse as a new icon that accompanies democratization. Since the reform began, many study centers and good governance projects have been created through universities, ranging from issues related to legal reform, judicial reform, decentralization, budgeting, to legal drafting. Likewise, non-governmental organizations also strongly transmit the idea of good governance through issues that are not much different.

Why is the transmission of good governance discourse so strongly promoted by the World Bank and then neatly transplanted by state and non-state agents? We can start dissecting it from its conceptual content, and then continued by mapping how this conceptual framework became dominantly imposed on southern countries, including Indonesia. In its 1989 report, the World Bank (Wiratraman, 2007) expressed the idea "Efforts to create

environmental capabilities and to build capacities will be discarded if the political context is not supportive. Ultimately, good governance requires political reform. This means joint action against corruption from the highest to the lowest levels. This can be done by setting a good example, by strengthening accountability, by supporting public debate, by maintaining a free press. This also means helping the development of grassroots and non-governmental organizations such as farmers' unions, associations and women's groups."

Using almost the same language style, the World Bank has also stated, "Good governance is symbolized by predictable, open and enlightened policy-making, a bureaucracy imbued with a professional ethos in acting." promotion of public facilities, rule of law, transparent processes, and strong civil society participating in the public interest. Poor governance on the other hand is characterized by arbitrary policy making, unaccountable bureaucracy, a legal system that is unfair and cannot be enforced, abuse of executive power, a civil society that cannot enjoy its public life and corruption. widespread." (World Bank 1994: vii).

In campaigning for good governance, the World Bank has programmed a learning program and has introduced the concept of governance. Good governance is a manual that is defined as the effective implementation of policies and provision of services that are responsive to the needs of its citizens. Good governance is attached to qualities, such as accountability, responsiveness, transparency and efficiency. It assumes the government's ability to manage social affairs, ensure peace, guarantee law and order, promote and create the necessary conditions for economic growth and ensure a minimum level of social security (World Bank 2002). Such a definition has actually remained and is strongly maintained to support the rules of the game that make markets work efficiently and more problematically, the World Bank corrects market failures (World Bank 1992).

A number of these documents show that the approach used by the World Bank, especially in emphasizing important issues of accountability, is actually aimed at seeking reforms for political stability and economic development that are needed in the market liberalization process. This concept of political economy actually focuses on the model of liberal democracy and economic liberalization, and good governance is also a neo-liberal model, namely 'good governance free market assistance' (Wiratraman 2008).

The neo-liberal character of good governance can be seen from its targets which always focus on efficient resource management and supporting the free market. The key elements are accountability, rule of law, transparency and participation. Indeed, these elements are also needs of the Indonesian people amidst the euphoria of reform, but these key elements actually harbor a big plan to dismantle the state's role in the public sector and replace it with a dominant private or private role. The matter of protecting human rights is not an important matter in this good governance scheme, even though the mandate of human rights responsibility rests on the main role of the state. Good governance will only place the market in a dominant position, and the public

affairs in question will also have been selected (read: pruned) based on the climate of market liberalization.

Why did good governance suddenly emerge, become prevalent and persist for a long time as a governance model in Indonesia that is widely discussed, followed and taught? Why is it that 'good governance' is quickly becoming familiar with the world of bureaucracy, the business world, the world of campuses and study centers (which also thrive like mushrooms in the rainy season), the world of activism of non-governmental organizations (especially those working on issues public policy and anti-corruption), and the strangest but true thing, almost all international funding institutions and donor countries are simultaneously pouring in (both debt and grants) billions of US dollars for good governance projects? In fact, the World Bank itself has actually failed to carry out good governance internally, because it is filled with systemic corruption and motives for exploitation of countries that owe it money.

The opinion states that the emergence of quite successful good governance projects is related to the success of the developmental state model among the newly industrialized countries in East Asia and Southeast Asia (Tshuma 1999; White 1987; Wade 1990). Another opinion says that neo-liberal ideology has accelerated after the collapse of communism and created an atmosphere conducive to the birth of governance as a development issue, and because neo-liberalism as the dominant ideology tries to construct 'politically locked-in neo-liberal reforms' (Gill, 1997).

The two opinions above are relevant to the emergence of good governance in Indonesia, because apart from development-oriented government policies during the New Order, the support of the World Bank and IMF in disbursing debt accompanied by special conditions complements Indonesia's position which leads to a market liberalization design. However, if we look more deeply, using hegemony analysis, it appears that good governance works by using rationality and technology of power to produce a smooth and effective machine for market liberalization efforts. Law as a political instrument is used to legalize the operation of the power machine, so it is far from reflecting a sense of justice and protection for the proletariat (Wiratraman, 2008). The World Bank itself promotes good governance in Indonesia through three doors: (i) CGI (Consultative Group on Indonesia); (ii) Partnership for Governance Reform; and (iii) Justice for the Poor. In the annual CGI forum, the World Bank leads and has the power to direct (dictate) economic policy (including urging the formation of legislative regulations). This can happen because the government is still receiving debt disbursement so that the debt prerequisites must be met as compensation. Meanwhile, the World Bank also works closely with UNDP and ADB as the main funding sponsor for the Partnership for Governance Reform (World Bank 2003). Through the multi-stakeholder group forum in this Partnership, the World Bank has been actively involved in creating a legal framework for development, such as judicial reform, legal reform, and the formation of new government institutions (World Bank 2003). The major influence of this partnership is precisely its hegemonic role as a funding agency for governance projects carried out not only by state

institutions, but also non-governmental organizations. Meanwhile, Justice for the Poor is an institution that was recently created by the World Bank to promote poverty reduction in Indonesia, especially an empowerment strategy for the poor through legal assistance.

For the World Bank, empowerment and legal awareness programs are important in providing the poor with access to justice. In matters of monitoring corruption, the World Bank itself chooses to focus more on projects that it funds itself (World Bank, 1997), such as the current PNPM (National Program for Community Empowerment). The last two institutions are vehicles for the World Bank to also participate in promoting human rights in Indonesia. Projects of governance reform through good governance tend to serve the promotion of consensus social and economic reform, especially by applying technocratic empowerment and the liberal language of participation. At this point, the discourse and direction of human rights trends are more in line with market liberalization. This is what is called the 'market friendly human rights paradigm' (Wiratraman, 2008).

The World Bank's strategy to maintain its hegemony is to reproduce knowledge about the rationality of good governance so as to facilitate the operation of its power technology through various entry points at the state, non-state and partnership levels. In reality, discourses on governance, legal reform and other public policies are constructed with including democracy, human rights, anti-poverty, anti-corruption, all of which feel suited to the atmosphere (trap) of reform that has been controlled by neo-liberal supporters. More complete is the technology of capital power which is able to mystify power imbalances and draw attention to the direction of 'good' reform, through funding programs to a number of state institutions, non-governmental organizations, as well as campuses through governance study centers. The temptation to access governance project funds is too great, so quite a few have changed the plans and work patterns of organizations receiving these funds. Donor-driven hegemony.

Apart from being formulated by referring to market mechanisms which are considered the most efficient in managing resources, good governance is also formulated as a democratic government pattern. In the language of the World Bank (1989 & 1992), apart from being caused by too large a government portion, development failure is also caused by undemocratic government, and state authority being personified in the person of one or a few leaders. Therefore, good governance also encourages democratization by forcing the state to share power with actors outside the state. It is admitted that there have been quite a lot of changes, including leaps in the formation and work of state institutions which increasingly complement the political landscape of the Indonesian state. Governance reform projects are carried out simultaneously, starting from efforts to reform laws, update performance standards, and reform other state institutions.

For the World Bank, reform of public sector administration and management is seen as important factors for strengthening development and economic growth. To support economic growth and a free market system, one

of the principle elements of good governance is the 'legal framework for development' (legislative framework for development) (World Bank 1992). In such a legislative framework, the rule of law is the main concept that is instrumentally and substantially important, because it concentrates on justice, fairness and freedom. The World Bank emphasizes a 'fair' legal system, which is conducive to balanced development (World Bank 1992: 29-30). This is why, not so surprisingly, the World Bank's perspective on good governance is related primarily to the legislative needs of commercial actors in the market.

In the domestic political arena, the implications of implementing good governance are also very clear. On the one hand, good governance has been proven to break down the arrogance of the state which has historically dominated society. The personification of state power in a small group of elites, the impasse in public access to public policies, and the weak enforcement of human rights have been broken by the wave of good governance. However, hegemonic power that oppresses the people is not automatically paralyzed. Hegemonic power only shifts from state control to private control (capital), which according to Korten (Pratikno, 2005) which in the case of Indonesia after the 1998-2002 crisis are multinational companies.

The implications of private hegemony for the general public are no less bad than the implications of state hegemony. Even though there are many poverty alleviation programs, the number of people below the poverty line has not experienced a significant reduction, or has even worsened in some countries. Hunger ulcers are still easily found when government practices have begun to implement the characteristics of good governance, such as participation and transparency. So, what does good governance mean for marginalized communities who are unable to become strong customers in this era of economic liberalization? This is where neo-liberalism works neatly. Filho and Johnston (Wiratraman, 2008) warn that under neo-liberalism, economic growth has declined, unemployment is widespread, inequality within and between countries is worsening everywhere, and marginalized groups will be massively oppressed from instability. economy.

In the Indonesian context, the pressure of neo-liberal public policy design is very clearly visible when legal reform efforts do not place the direction of change on a system that is more just for the people at large, but rather obey market interests or tastes in creating a business climate. The only thing that is most painful for workers is the establishment of special judicial institutions for workers through the Law on Settlement of Industrial Relations Disputes (PPHI), the Law on Educational Legal Entities, the Oil and Gas Law, the Investment Law, etc. The legal reform project sponsored by the World Bank, in its implementation, of course has an impact on public administration and management practices, which according to Prasodjo (Kurniawan 2006) takes the form of de-bureaucratization of internal organizations, modernization of the bureaucracy, and increasing the capacity of the bureaucratic apparatus.

The public sector is faced with a new set of expectations from society, that the public sector or government needs to be managed efficiently (Rakhmat, 2009). This condition is certainly a prerequisite for improving the quality of

public services on the one hand and on the other hand a space for community participation in public activities (Kurniawan, 2006). All of these phenomena are implications of the World Bank's good governance projects, which are always aimed at disciplining governance that is oriented toward loyalty to market liberalization. The market mechanism that is campaigned for in good governance turns out to be immanipulation becomes a pseudo-procedure without the state's capacity to discipline it.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Not all of the problems described above are caused by the good governance campaign which emphasizes 'sound development management' which is a "trap" of the neo-liberal agenda. Whether we realize it or not, the concepts and ideas of good governance have become the "grand narrative" of public bureaucratic reform in Indonesia. However, these problems developed as a result of discourse and practice of public policy reform in Indonesia that was not adequately contextualized, reform ideas were fragmented, and reform ideas did not grow from actors at the lower levels. This article is also not intended to say that external pressure is not important in the government reform agenda in Indonesia. However, a reform agenda that is trapped in changes in government technicalities and project bureaucracy will result in the public policy agenda losing its spirit and ultimate goals that are more meaningful for society.

The arguments of neo-liberal advocates stating that guaranteeing individual political rights and the democratization process will support the development of good governance are not wrong. However, this package must be combined with individual social and economic rights as an inseparable, integrative package. Guaranteeing social and economic rights cannot be implemented as a product of good governance alone, but must be part of the process of developing good governance. Therefore, as initiated by Mahbub ul Haq (Pratikno, 2005), the development of good governance needs to be combined with the concept of humane governance which includes "good political, economic and civic governance".

This idea needs to be explored further, and needs to be contextualized with the potential and problems of contemporary Indonesia. At the same time, Denhart and Denhardt's (2003) idea of The New Public Service needs to be taken into account as an initial initiative. In essence, maintaining the individual's position as a citizen and asking the government to be more responsible for ensuring social and economic rights is something vital, apart from political rights.

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